

Condensed Thiophene Derivatives. Part-II*. Formylation of Dibenzothiophene

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Direct formylation of dibenzothiophene is reported.

NO systematic attempts at formylation of dibenzothiophene have been reported. Hartough and Meisel¹ have proposed that various substituted carboxaldehydes may be synthesised from the corresponding acid chlorides by the Rosenmund reduction although none are so far reported. Dibenzothiophene was recovered in experiments on attempted formylation by conventional methods, viz. (a) N,N-dimethylformamide and phosphorus oxychloride², and (b) zinc cyanide and hydrogen chloride³. Riech and Co-workers⁴ provided a useful method of formylation of aromatic heterocyclic compounds. Formylation of dibenzothiophene was carried out accordingly with dichloromethyl methyl ether in the presence of aluminium chloride at 0°. This afforded three different compounds identified as (I; major, m.p. 125-26°), (III; m.p. 236-37°) and (II; as viscous liquid) in addition to unchanged dibenzothiophene. These carboxaldehydes (I, II, III) are characterised and identified by way of oxidation to related acids (IV, V, VI) and then subsequent preparation of methyl esters or alternatively by reduction of (I, II, & III) to corresponding methyl dibenzothiophenes (V', VIII, & IX).

- I : $R_1 = \text{CHO}, R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 II : $R_2 = \text{CHO}, R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 III : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{CHO}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 IV : $R_1 = \text{COOH}, R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 V : $R_2 = \text{COOH}, R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 VI : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{COOH}, R_2 = \text{H}$
 VII : $R_1 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 VIII : $R_2 = \text{CH}_3, R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 IX : $R_1 = R_3 = \text{CH}_3, R_2 = \text{H}$
 X : $R_1 = \text{CH} = \text{CHCOOH}, R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 XI : $R_2 = \text{CH} = \text{CHCOOH}, R_1 = R_3 = \text{H}$

To illustrate, the major product melting at 125-26° was identified as dibenzothiophene-2-carboxaldehyde (I; $\nu_{\text{ald. carbonyl}} 1705 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). (I) gave a 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and on oxidation by the method of Hey and Lobo⁵ converted into (IV) which on subsequent esterification with diazomethane yields corresponding methyl dibenzothiophene-2-carboxylate. The authenticity of the structure (I) was further confirmed by reducing it by Wolff-Kishner method to give (VII). Similarly, the viscous liquid identified as dibenzothiophene-3-carboxaldehyde (II) ($\nu_{\text{ald. carbonyl}} 1708 \text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The product melting at 236-37° analysed for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{S}$ and identified as dibenzothiophene-2,8-dicarboxaldehyde (i.r. absorption at 1700 cm^{-1} , split for dicarboxaldehydic group). The product (III) gave a mono 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone and a dialdoxime in alcohol. On reduction by Wolff-Kishner method (IX) was obtained. The authenticity of the structure (III) was confirmed by conversion into known 2,8-dimethyl dibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide. (IX) was characterised by the preparation of 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex.

The carboxaldehydes (I) & (II) are converted into related cinnamic acids (X) & (XI) by Doebner's modification with malonic acid. Further work with these acids are in progress.

Experimental

*All m. ps. or b. ps. are uncorrected. Unless otherwise mentioned, the i. r. spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer, Model 237 in KBr discs.

Formylation of Dibenzothiophene: A mixture of dibenzothiophene (4.0 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (6.0g.) in dry methylene chloride (30.0 ml) at 0° was stirred during dropwise addition of dichloromethyl methyl ether (6.0 ml.; 70%) over a period of 15 min.; when the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased (15 min.), the reaction mixture was immediately poured on crushed ice which resulted into layers. The organic layer was separated out and the aqueous layer was extracted with chloroform and combined organic layers

* Part-I, is Chatterjea and Gandhi, This Journal, 1977, 54, 719.

were washed successively with water (2×30.0 ml.), sod. bicarbonate solution (2×30.0 ml.: 2N) and water (30.0 ml.). After drying over baked MgSO₄, the solvents were evaporated and the remainder taken up in benzene. The insoluble material was filtered out, the benzene solution was concentrated, cooled and chromatographed through an activated alumina column. It was eluted with benzene. Out of eight fractions, the first two fractions on evaporation of solvent gave unreacted dibenzothiophene, m.p. 99-100°.

Next three fractions gave an oil which was subjected to bulb distillation at a bath temp. 240-50°/2 mm. to give a light yellow oil. The oil on trituration and crystallisation from MeOH gave pale yellow prisms (0.8 g.), m.p. 125-26° and were identified to be *dibenzothiophene-2-carboxaldehyde* (I). (Found: C, 73.69; H, 3.87. C₁₃H₈OS requires: C, 73.58. H, 3.80%; i.r. Spectrum: Carboxaldehydic absorption at 1705 cm⁻¹. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative was crystallised from a large volume of AcOH in orange crystalline solid, m.p. above 300°, (Found: N, 14.31; C₁₉H₁₂N₄O₄S requires: N, 14.28%).

The remaining methanolic mother liquor from 3rd., 4th. & 5th. fractions was evaporated to give an oil which on distillation at a bath temp. of 220-30°/2 mm. gave a light yellow mobile liquid which was identified as *dibenzothiophene-3-carboxaldehyde* (II). (Found: C, 73.63; H, 3.86. C₁₃H₈OS requires: C, 73.58; H, 3.80%). i.r. Spectrum: ν_{aldehyde} 1708 cm⁻¹. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative from dibenzothiophene-3-carboxaldehyde was crystallised from AcOH in an orange solid, m.p. 260-62°. (Found: N, 14.31. C₁₉H₁₂N₄O requires: N, 14.28%). The rest three fractions on concentration and keeping at r.t. for 1 hr. gave a yellowish solid, which was crystallised from benzene in light yellow prisms (0.6 g.), m.p. 236-37°. It was characterised and identified as *dibenzothiophene-2,8-dicarboxaldehyde* (III). (Found: C, 70.16; H, 3.72. C₁₄H₈O₂S requires: C, 70.00; H, 3.36%). i.r. Spectrum: ν_{aldehyde} 1700 cm⁻¹. The *mono* 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from a large volume of AcOH in an orange solid which melted above 300°. (Found: N, 13.43. C₂₀H₁₂N₄O₆S requires: N, 13.53. C₂₀H₁₂N₄O₆S requires: N, 13.66%). This clearly showed that only one carboxaldehydic group was involved in the formation of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivative. *Dibenzothiophene-2,8-dialdoxime* crystallised from EtOH in colourless prisms, m.p. 246-48°. (Found: N, 10.41. C₁₄H₁₀N₂O₂S requires: N, 10.37%).

Dibenzothiophene-2-carboxylic Acid (IV): *Dibenzothiophene-2-carboxaldehyde* (0.64 g.) was converted into the corresponding 2-carboxylic acid by oxidising it with boiling silver nitrate solution (16.0 ml.; 8%) for 3 min. Sod. hydroxide solution (5.0 ml.; 15%) was added slowly till the free silver deposited on the inner walls of the flask completely disintegrated. The resulting alkaline mixture was boiled for 2 hrs., cooled, filtered and acidified to give the required *acid* (IV; 0.35 g.) which was finally crystallised from AcOH, m.p. 251-52° (lit.⁶, m.p. 253°). (Found: C, 68.35; H, 3.66. C₁₃H₈O₂S

requires: C, 68.42; H, 3.33%). *Methyl dibenzothiophene-2-carboxylate* prepared through diazomethane, melted at 80-81° (lit.⁶, m.p. 74-75°). (Found: C, 69.35; H, 4.02. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₀O₂S: C, 69.42; H, 16%).

Dibenzothiophene-3-carboxylic Acid (V) similarly prepared and crystallised from EtOH in prismatic needles, m.p. 299-305° (decomp.; lit.⁷, m.p. 300-305°). (Found: C, 68.51; H, 3.45. C₁₃H₈O₂S requires: 68.42; H, 3.53%). *Methyl dibenzothiophene-3-carboxylate* crystallised from a mixture of MeOH & EtOH (1:1) to give colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 110-12° (lit.⁷, m.p. 128-29°). (Found: C, 69.34; H, 3.56. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₀O₂S: C, 69.42; H, 4.16%).

2-Methyldibenzothiophene (VII): The 2-carboxaldehyde isomer (0.5 g.) in dry diethylene glycol (5.0 ml.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (1.0 ml.; 99-100%) and boiled for 2 hrs. On cooling, the colourless *hydrazone* separated out. To this, pot. hydroxide (1.0 g.) was added after removing water from the system by distillation and heated to 190-200° for about 3 hrs. till evolution of nitrogen ceased. The mixture was cooled to r.t. and diluted with water and a crystalline mass separated out which was crystallised from EtOH as colourless plates (0.2 g.), m.p. 86-87° (lit.⁸, m.p. 85.5°). (Found: C, 78.67; H, 5.12. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₀S: C, 78.77; H, 5.09%). The *picrate* crystallised from EtOH in beautiful yellow needles, m.p. 115-16° (lit.⁸, m.p. 117-18°). (Found: N, 9.92. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₀S. C₆H₈N₂O₇: N, 9.83%).

3-Methyldibenzothiophene (VIII): similarly prepared and distilled under reduced pressure at 140-50°/2 mm. (Found: C, 78.81; H, 5.20. Calc. for C₁₃H₁₀S: C, 78.77; H, 5.09%). The *picrate* of 3-methyldibenzothiophene crystallised from EtOH in light yellow needles, m.p. 95-96° (lit.⁸, m.p. 97°). (Found: N, 9.96. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₀S. C₆H₈N₂O₇: N, 9.83%).

2,8-Dimethyldibenzothiophene (IX) crystallised from pet. ether in colourless short needles, m.p. 154-55° (lit.⁹, m.p. 121-2°). (Found: C, 79.15; H, 5.87. C₁₄H₁₂S requires: C, 79.25; H, 5.66%). It is quite possible that our product is probably purer than that reported by Armarego and Turner or it may be a polymorphic form. The 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone complex crystallised from benzene in orange needles, m.p. 210-11°. (Found: N, 8.20. C₁₄H₁₂S. C₁₃H₈N₃O₇ requires N; 8.12%).

2,8-Dimethyldibenzothiophene-5,5-dioxide: To a cold solution of glacial AcOH (3.0 ml.) and hydrogen peroxide (2.0 ml.; 20 vol.) was added 2,8-dimethyldibenzothiophene (0.1 g.) and refluxed for 2 hrs. The reaction mixture was diluted with cold water to give a yellowish precipitate which was filtered and crystallised from dilute AcOH in colourless needles (0.05 g.), m.p. 294-295° (lit.⁹ m.p. 297-98°). (Found: C, 68.91; H, 5.04. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₂O₂S: C, 68.84; H, 4.95%).

Dibenzothiophene-2(B)-acrylic acid (X) : Catalytic amount of piperidine was added to a mixture of dibenzothiophene-2-carboxaldehyde (0.21 g.) and malonic acid (0.11 g.) in dry pyridine (5.0 ml.) and was heated on water-bath for 5-6 hrs. It was cooled, diluted with water and the acrylic acid (X) was obtained on acidification with dilute hydrochloric (5N). It was crystallised from EtOH in prisms (0.2 g.), m.p. 251°. (Found: C, 70.92 ; H, 4.01. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2S$ requires: C, 70.86 ; H, 3.96%).

Dibenzothiophene-3(B)-acrylic Acid (XI) similarly prepared, crystallised from EtOH in colourless prisms, m.p. 238-39°. (Found: C, 70.88 ; H, 4.12. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2S$ requires: C, 70.86 ; H, 3.96%).

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